

Incorporation of Cr^{III} into a Keggin polyoxometalate as a chemical strategy to stabilize a labile {Cr^{III}O₄} tetrahedral conformation and promote unattended single-ion magnet properties

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Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: Polyoxometalates (POMs) provide rigid and highly symmetric coordination sites and can be used as a strategy for stabilization of magnetic ions. Herein, we report a new member of the Keggin archetype – the Cr-centered Keggin anion [α -CrW₁₂O₄₀]⁵⁻ (CrW₁₂) – with the unusual tetrahedral coordination of Cr^{III} reported for the first time in POMs conferring unattended magnetic properties. POM chemistry has recently presented excellent examples of single molecule and single ion magnets (SMMs and SIMs) as well as molecular spin qubits; however, the majority of POM-based SIMs reported to date contain lanthanoid ions. CrW₁₂, as the first example of chromium (III) SIM, exhibits slow relaxation of magnetization and quantum tunneling with a single ion magnetic behavior even above 10 K with an energy barrier for the reversal of the magnetization of 3.0 K. The first 3d-metal SIM based on a non-lacunary Keggin anion is the foundation for a new research area in POM chemistry.

Cr^{III} ions in inorganic compounds exhibit a strong tendency to adopt an octahedral coordination¹ owing to high ligand field stabilization energy (LFSE) for a 3d³ ion with ⁴A₂ ground state. The equivalent tetrahedral complexes, which have a ground state that is degenerate, are not stable and the tetrahedral coordination has been confirmed only in blue-colored diopsides and Cr^{III}[μ_3 -O₄] cubanes.² The confinement of Cr^{III} inside certain molecular cages, such as polyoxometalates (POMs), can help to stabilize a tetrahedral coordination geometry. A handful of chromium-containing POMs are known to date, all exhibiting an octahedral coordination of Cr^{III}.³⁻⁵ In 1962, Brown reported the preparation of 12-tungstochromic(III) acid H₃[α -CrW₁₂O₄₀] \cdot nH₂O with Cr^{III} ions in tetrahedral ligand field.⁶ The conclusion of the formation of [α -CrW₁₂O₄₀] was solely based on the appearance of a weak band assigned to (Cr–O)_{Td} at 8300 cm⁻¹ in the near-infrared spectrum of [α -CrW₁₂O₄₀]⁵⁻ and was subsequently questioned.⁷ To the best of our knowledge, the crystal structure of [α -CrW₁₂O₄₀]⁵⁻

with a tetrahedral {CrO₄} unit in POMs has not been documented yet.

The incorporation of magnetic units into the POM architectures is of considerable interest since POMs as ligands may shield the magnetic core from interaction with other molecules, creating a single molecule magnet (SMM).⁸ SMMs based on POMs reported so far can be divided into three groups, representing: 1) a number of 3d-transition metal ions, which can be connected through oxo-bridges forming magnetic clusters of variable nuclearities and high symmetries;⁹ 2) a number of lanthanoid ions in order to give rise to a lanthanoid complex in which 4f-magnetic ions are submitted to the crystal field created by POM ligands;⁸ 3) a mixed-valence framework hosting a number of electrons that are usually delocalized over all the framework structure.¹⁰ The possibility of constructing nanomagnets using a single lanthanoid ion has been demonstrated for both polyoxotungstates ([Ln(W₅O₁₈)₂]⁹⁻,¹¹ [Ln(β -SiW₁₁O₃₉)₂]^{13-,12} [LnW₃₀O₁₁₀]^{12-,13}) and polyoxomolybdates ([Ln(β -Mo₈O₂₆)₂]^{5-,14} [Ln{Mo₅O₁₃(OMe)₄NNC₆H₄-p-NO₂}₂]^{3-,14}). Although a growing number of first-row d-block single ion magnets (SIM) has been reported,¹⁵ d-block SIMs based on POMs are particularly rare.¹⁶⁻¹⁷ Even though there are a few examples of heteropolynuclear SMMs containing chromium(III) centers,¹⁸ there are no reported chromium(III) SIMs.

Herein, we report the first Cr^{III}-centered Keggin-type anion [α -CrW₁₂O₄₀]⁵⁻ (CrW₁₂), representing a new member of the Keggin ([XM₁₂O₄₀]ⁿ⁻ = [XO₄M₁₂O₃₆]ⁿ⁻, X: heteroatom; M: Mo, W, V or Nb) POM family. CrW₁₂ was characterized by elemental analysis, single-crystal and powder X-ray diffraction analysis, IR spectroscopy, thermogravimetric analysis, electrospray ionization mass-spectrometry, cyclic voltammetry, X-ray absorption and photoelectron spectroscopy, UV-Vis-NIR electronic spectroscopy, high-frequency and -field electron paramagnetic resonance, magnetic susceptibility measurements and DFT calculations (see SI, Figs. S1-S14, Tables S1-S5). The {Cr^{III}O₄} unit is stabilized inside the Keggin cavity, which causes a slow relaxation of mag-

netization. This type of system, where a POM cavity isolates the SIM unit from the environment, is an interesting approach to acquire direct and explicit information about the mechanisms that govern the SIM behavior.

CrW₁₂ was isolated as double salt Na_{2.4}(TMA)₃[α -CrW₁₂O₄₀]_{0.6}[α -H₂W₁₂O₄₀]_{0.4}·37H₂O (TMA: tetramethylammonium, (CH₃)₄N⁺) from the system Cr^{III} – WO₄²⁻ (c = 0.04 M) – H⁺ – Tris-NH₂ with a molar ratio of 1 Cr^{III} : 10 W^{VI}: 12 H⁺ : 5 Tris-NH₂ (Tris-NH₂ - tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane, H₂NC(CH₂OH)₃) at the final pH of 7.5. Interestingly, when the pH was adjusted to 7.5 with NaOH instead of Tris-NH₂ or with a phosphate buffer, **CrW₁₂** could not be isolated (Scheme S1). The use of phosphate buffer most likely leads to the formation of lacunary [α -PW₁₂O₄₀]³⁻. The failure to crystallize the target product with NaOH indicates the importance of buffering during the **CrW₁₂** synthesis due to the complex hydrolysis equilibria in POT solution. The formation of mono lacunary anions in unbuffered system was also shown by ESI-MS (Figure S2).

CrW₁₂ possesses a typical disordered α -Keggin structure (CCDC 1913668, Fig. 1). The central cation Cr^{III} is surrounded by eight half-occupied oxygen atoms (Fig. 1 A), thus reducing its effective coordination number to four. This disorder of the oxygen atoms in the Keggin ion was first mentioned in 1984¹⁹ and reported for many Keggin structures with different heteroatoms, e.g. Si⁴⁺²⁰ or P⁵⁺²¹. The cubic environment around the central heteroatom X can be formed from the superimposition of one tetrahedrally coordinated X in one unit cell with another X tetrahedron (just oppositely oriented) in the neighboring unit cell.

Figure 1. The **CrW₁₂** anion. A) Ball-and-stick representation including the crystallographic disorder in {CrO₄}. B) Polyhedral representation. Color code: W, blue; Cr, green; O, red, orange, purple.

The Cr^{III} site occupancy amounts to 60 % based on the X-ray data. This indicates that an alternative population of the central Keggin tetrahedron with Cr^{III} or two protons is most likely. The synthesized compound can be described as a double salt of **CrW₁₂** and the metatungstate anion [α -H₂W₁₂O₄₀]⁶⁻ (**H₂W₁₂**). The alternating occupancy with two hetero ions in a Keggin anion was previously described for Cu^{II} and two protons in [α -Cu_{0.4}(H₂)_{0.6}W₁₂O₄₀]⁶⁻.²²

The direct current (dc) magnetic behavior of **CrW₁₂** is shown in Figure 2 as plot of $\chi_M T$ against T , where $\chi_M T$ is the molar magnetic susceptibility, and of the magnetization (M) versus H/T at different applied dc fields. At room temperature, $\chi_M T$ of **CrW₁₂** amounts to 0.65 cm³·mol⁻¹·K and remains constant by cooling down to 50 K. This value is distinctly lower than the spin-only value (1.874 cm³·mol⁻¹·K) for a high-spin d³ ion supporting the partial occupancy of Cr^{III} site in **CrW₁₂**.

Since the paramagnetic Cr^{III} in **CrW₁₂** is kept isolated from other neighbors inside the polyoxotungstate, the decrease of $\chi_M T$ below 12 K and the non-superposition of the curves of the reduced magnetization can be attributed only to a weak zero-field splitting (zfs). The simultaneous analysis of all data through the spin Hamiltonian: $\hat{H} = D(\hat{S}_z^2 - S(S+1)/3) + E(\hat{S}_x^2 - \hat{S}_y^2) + g\beta\hat{H}S$, provided a good agreement between experimental and

simulated curves with the best-fit parameters: $|D| = +0.98$ cm⁻¹, $E/D = 0.095$, and $g = 2.005$. Although there is no doubt about the presence of a zfs in **CrW₁₂**, the sign of the axial component (D) is uncertain.

Figure 2. Magnetometry of **CrW₁₂**. Temperature dependence of $\chi_M T$ and the magnetization curves (inset) for **CrW₁₂**: (o, ●) experimental; (-) best-fit curves to the experimental data using the parameters provided in the text. The $\chi_M T$ value supports the partial occupancy of Cr^{III} and corresponds to 36 %.

In order to more accurately determine zfs in **CrW₁₂**, we used high-frequency and -field electron paramagnetic resonance (HF-EPR). Although the spectral quality was moderate at best, a low-temperature, multi-frequency experiment in the V-band range (Fig. 3) delivered a direct measure of zfs by observing a near-zero field absorption between the $\pm 1/2$ and $\pm 3/2$ Kramers doublets at 65 ± 1 GHz = 2.16(3) cm⁻¹. This value represents the parameter $\Delta = 2(D^2 + 3E^2)^{1/2}$ for an $S = 3/2$ spin state. In order to deconvolute Δ into D and E we performed standard X-band EPR (Fig. S6), which resulted in spectra originating from the $\pm 1/2$ Kramers doublet only, and typical for the case $|D| > h\nu$ where h is Planck's constant and ν is the EPR operating frequency (9.47 GHz = ~ 0.3 cm⁻¹). The spectra could be satisfactorily simulated using $|D| = 1.07$ and $|E| = 0.07$ cm⁻¹ (rhombicity factor $E/D = 0.07$). The axial parameter D is in excellent agreement with the magnetometric result. These parameters were then used in plotting the field vs. frequency (or energy) dependence of the EPR turning points, confirming their accuracy (Fig. S7). Given the modest zfs magnitude, and the relatively low EPR frequencies employed, it was not possible to unequivocally determine the sign of D . A perfect cancellation of large contributions to zfs in an ideal tetrahedral high-spin d^3 system is broken due to a small distortions and a partial charge transfer in the ground state from the highly charged oxo-groups bound to a high-spin Cr^{III} ion, which can accept electrons, with an unstable geometry that facilitates this electronic drain (see SI and Table S4). UV-Vis-NIR solid reflectance spectrum of **CrW₁₂** also supports a moderate charge-transfer from the oxo groups to the Cr^{III} ion and a presence of a high-spin d^3 Cr^{III} ion in a tetrahedral coordination environment (see SI and Fig. S14). Alternating current (ac) magnetic susceptibility measurements below 10 K did not show out-of-phase magnetic susceptibility χ_M'' signals at frequencies up to 10000 Hz in the absence of an applied dc field. However, the suppression of fast tunneling of the magnetization (QTM) by the application of an external dc field (H_{dc} , 1000 and 2500 G) resulted in a set of frequency-dependent signals in plots of χ_M'' vs. T (Fig. S8). This slow relaxation of the magnetization in mononuclear complexes is characteristic for SIMs. The relaxation times (τ) at each temperature were extracted from χ_M'' vs. frequencies (ν) plots, in which χ_M''

reaches its highest value (Fig. S9). The obtained data in the form of $\{T, \nu\}$ pairs was used to build Arrhenius plots (Fig. S10), showing a linear dependence that can only be described by a unique relaxation process following an Arrhenius law, $\tau^{-1} = \tau_0^{-1} \exp(-E_a/kT)$, where k is the Boltzmann constant and E_a the energy barrier governing the spin reversal. The E_a and τ_0 values calculated for CrW_{12} (Table S3) are in the range of those found in octahedral and tetrahedral complexes with first-row transition metal ions. In both magnetic fields, the E_a values are about 3.0 cm^{-1} , which is the energy barrier calculated from $|D| = 1.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, a value close to those derived from the EPR study and magnetometry. However, an energy barrier for the spin reversal governed for an Orbach mechanism is only possible for a negative value of D , which could not be experimentally confirmed. SIMs with positive D values or even with an $S = 1/2$ ground state are increasingly common, however, the relaxation mechanism governing their spin dynamics is still under discussion.^{15, 23-25}

Figure 3. HFEPR spectra of CrW_{12} at 4.5 K and indicated frequencies in the vicinity of the zero-field transition between the $\pm 1/2$ and $\pm 3/2$ Kramers doublets. The resonances appearing between 2 and 3 T depending on frequency ($g \sim 1.95$) belong to a different spin species, which has a much lower anisotropy (about 0.1 cm^{-1}) and thus represents a small fraction of total absorption despite its amplitude, signifying low abundance.

Only two cases of POM-based d-block (Fe^{III} and Co^{II}) SIMs has been described in literature.¹⁶⁻¹⁷ The single-ion magnet behavior is unusual in high-spin Fe^{III} complexes and rarely encountered for the systems based on POMs, however, this effect is well known for Fe^{III} porphyrin complexes.²⁶ In contrast, in CrW_{12} the zfs is induced through a unique and bizarre tetrahedral geometry for a d^3 ion. Compared with SIMs based on third-row transition metal ions (Table S5), the energy barrier for CrW_{12} is small, but more importantly, the temperature for the slow relaxation of magnetization is above 10 K, which places it in the same range or better than other analogs. The chemical surrounding can hamper, randomly modify or even abolish the slow relaxation of magnetization. In our case, the use of POMs as shielding ligands is a strategy to avoid these unwanted interactions. Moreover, tetrahedral high-spin Cr^{III} complexes with a small zfs , as in CrW_{12} , feature both allowed and forbidden transitions and can therefore be applied as a qubit.²⁷

The existence of CrW_{12} demonstrates that Cr^{III} can adopt a tetrahedral coordination in the Keggin cavity and opens a new perspective for Cr-centered lacunary POMs. The Keggin cavity is capable to stabilize an *a priori* unstable tetrahedral geometry for a high-spin d^3 ion, which results in a single ion magnet behavior.

These novel properties of POMs enhance the relevance of these inorganic compounds in molecular magnetism because a variety of a new series of 3d-metal SIMs can be foreseen by a suitable choice of POM ligands.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

Synthesis details and spectroscopic data along with structural characterizations of the new compound (PDF).

Accession Code CCDC 1913668 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif, or by emailing data_request@ccdc.cam.ac.uk, or by contacting The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; fax: +44 1223 336033.

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Notes

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REFERENCES

- 1 D. Waroquiers, X. Gonze, G.-M. Rignanese, C. Welker-Nieuwoudt, F. Rosowski, M. Göbel, S. Schenk, P. Degelmann, R. Andre, R. Glaum, G. Hautier. Statistical analysis of coordination environments in oxides. *Chem. Mater.* **2017**, *29*, 8346–8360. doi: 10.1021/acs.chemmater.7b02766
- 2 A. M. Beale, D. Grandjean, J. Kornatowski, P. Glatzel, F. M. F. de Groot, B. M. Weckhuysen. Unusual coordination behavior of Cr^{3+} in microporous aluminophosphates. *J. Phys. Chem. B*, **2006**, *110*, 716–722. doi: 10.1021/jp0531006
- 3 H.-J. Lunk. Discovery, properties and applications of chromium and its compounds. *ChemTexts*, 2015, *1*, 6. doi: 10.1007/s40828-015-0007-z
- 4 a) W. Liu, J. H. Christian, R. Al-Oweini, B. S. Bassil, J. van Tol, M. Atanasov, F. Neese, N. S. Dalal, U. Kortz. Synthesis, detailed characterization, and theoretical understanding of mononuclear chromium(III)-containing polyoxotungstates $[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}(\text{HX}^{\text{V}}\text{W}_7\text{O}_{28})_2]^{13-}$ ($\text{X} = \text{P}, \text{As}$) with exceptionally large magnetic anisotropy. *Inorg. Chem.* **2014**, *53*, 9274–9283; doi:10.1021/ic501385r (b) W. Liu, R. Al-Oweini, K. Meadows, B. S. Bassil, Z. Lin, J. H. Christian, N. S. Dalal, A. M. Bossoh, I. M. Mbomekallé, P. de Oliveira, J. Iqbal, U. Kortz. Cr^{III} -substituted heteropo-

- ly-16-tungstates $[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}_2(\text{B}-\beta\text{-X}^{\text{IV}}\text{W}_8\text{O}_{31})_2]^{14-}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Si}, \text{Ge}$): magnetic, biological, and electrochemical studies. *Inorg. Chem.* **2016**, *55*, 10936-10946. doi: 10.1021/acs.inorgchem.6b01458
- 5 (a) A. Perloff. Crystal structure of sodium hexamolybdochromate(III) octahydrate, $\text{Na}_3(\text{CrMo}_6\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_6)\cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ *Inorg. Chem.* **1970**, *9*, 2228-2239; doi: 10.1021/ic50092a006 (b) W. Liu, Z. Lin, B. S. Bassil, R. Al-Oweini, U. Kortz. Synthesis and Structure of Hexatungstochromate(III), $[\text{H}_3\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_6\text{O}_{24}]^{6-}$ *Chimia* **2015**, *69*, 537-540. doi: 10.2533/chimia.2015.537 (c) N. I. Gumerova, T. Caldera Fraile, A. Roller, G. Giester, M. Pascual-Borràs, C. A. Ohlin, A. Rompel. Direct single- and double-side triol-functionalization of the mixed type Anderson polyoxo- tungstate $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3\text{W}_6\text{O}_{24}]^{6-}$. *Inorg. Chem.* **2019**, *58*, 106-113; doi: 10.1021/acs.inorgchem.8b01740
- 6 D. H. Brown. The preparation, properties, structure, and spectra of 12-tungstochromic(III) acid. *J. Chem. Soc.* **1962**, *0*, 3322-3324. doi: 10.1039/JR9620003322
- 7 Nomiya, M. Miwa. Undecatungstomanganate and undecatungstochromate. *Polyhedron* **1984**, *3*, 1161-1163. doi: 10.1016/S0277-5387(00)88075-4
- 8 J. M. Clemente-Juan, E. Coronado, A. Gaita-Ariño. Magnetic polyoxometalates: from molecular magnetism to molecular spintronics and quantum computing. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2012**, *41*, 7464-7478. doi: 10.1039/C2CS35205B
- 9 C. Ritchie, A. Ferguson, H. Nojiri, H. N. Miras, Y.-F. Song, D.-L. Long, E. Burkholder, M. Murrice, P. Kögerler, E. K. Brechin, L. Cronin. Polyoxometalate-mediated self-assembly of single-molecule magnets: $\{[\text{XW}_6\text{O}_{34}][\text{Mn}(\text{III})_4\text{Mn}(\text{II})_2\text{O}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\}^{12-}$. *Angew. Chem.* **2008**, *47*, 5609-5612. doi: 10.1002/anie.200801281
- 10 J. Lehmann, A. Gaita-Ariño, E. Coronado, D. Loss. Spin qubits with electrically gated polyoxometalate molecules. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2007**, *2*, 312-317. doi: 10.1038/nnano.2007.110
- 11 M. A. AlDamen, J. M. Clemente-Juan, E. Coronado, C. Martí-Castaldo, A. Gaita-Ariño. Mononuclear lanthanide single-molecule magnets based on polyoxometalates. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, *130*, 8874-8875. doi: 10.1021/ja801659m
- 12 M. A. AlDamen, S. Cardona-Serra, J. M. Clemente-Juan, E. Coronado, A. Gaita-Ariño, C. Martí-Gastaldo, F. Luis, O. Montero. Mononuclear lanthanide single molecule magnets based on the polyoxometalates $[\text{Ln}(\text{W}_5\text{O}_{18})_2]^{9-}$ and $[\text{Ln}(\beta_2\text{-SiW}_{11}\text{O}_{39})_2]^{13-}$ ($\text{Ln}^{\text{III}} = \text{Tb}, \text{Dy}, \text{Ho}, \text{Er}, \text{Tm}, \text{and Yb}$). *Inorg. Chem.* **2009**, *48*, 3467-3479. doi: 10.1021/ic801630z
- 13 S. Cardona-Serra, J. M. Clemente-Juan, E. Coronado, A. Gaita-Ariño, A. Camón, M. Evangelisti, F. Luis, M. J. Martínez-Pérez, J. Sesé. Lanthanoid single-ion magnets based on polyoxometalates with a 5-fold symmetry: the series $[\text{LnP}_5\text{W}_{30}\text{O}_{110}]^{12-}$ ($\text{Ln}^{3+} = \text{Tb}, \text{Dy}, \text{Ho}, \text{Er}, \text{Tm}, \text{and Yb}$). *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 14982-14990. doi: 10.1021/ja305163t
- 14 J. J. Baldoví, Y. Duan, C. Bustos, S. Cardona-Serra, P. Gouzerh, R. Villanneau, G. Gontard, J. M. Clemente-Juan, A. Gaita-Ariño, C. Giménez-Saiz, A. Proust, E. Coronado. Single ion magnets based on lanthanoid polyoxomolybdate complexes. *Dalton Trans.* **2016**, *45*, 16653-16660. doi: 10.1039/C6DT02258H
- 15 J. M. Frost, K. L. M. Harriman, M. Murugesu. The rise of 3-d single-ion magnets in molecular magnetism: towards materials from molecules? *Chem. Sci.* **2016**, *7*, 2470-2491. doi: 10.1039/C5SC03224E
- 16 R. Sato, K. Suzuki, T. Minato, M. Shinoe, K. Yamaguchi, N. Mizuno. Field-induced slow magnetic relaxation of octahedrally coordinated mononuclear Fe(III)-, Co(II)-, and Mn(III)-containing polyoxometalates. *Chem. Commun.* **2015**, *51*, 4081-4084. doi: 10.1039/C4CC09435B
- 17 T. Minato, D. Aravena, E. Ruiz, K. Yamaguchi, N. Mizuno, K. Suzuki. Effect of heteroatoms on field-induced slow magnetic relaxation of mononuclear Fe^{III} ($S = 5/2$) ions within polyoxometalates. *Inorg. Chem.* **2018**, *57*, 6957-6964. doi: 10.1021/acs.inorgchem.8b00644
- 18 J. J. Sokol, A. G. Hee, J. R. Long. A cyano-bridged single-molecule magnet: slow magnetic relaxation in a trigonal prismatic $\text{MnMo}_6(\text{CN})_{18}$ cluster. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2002**, *124*, 7656-7657. doi: 10.1021/ja0263846
- 19 T. Evans, M. T. Pope. Reinterpretation of five recent crystal structures of heteropoly and isopoly complexes: divanadododecamolybdo-phosphate, trivanadoenecamolybdophosphate, "gamma-dodecatungstophosphate", the dodecamolybdate-dodecamolybdomolybdate blue complex, and dihydrogen decavanadate. *Inorg. Chem.* **1984**, *23*, 501-504. doi: 10.1021/ic00172a024
- 20 S. Roy, S. Sarkar, J. Pan, U. V. Waghmare, R. Dhanya, C. Narayana, S. C. Peter. Crystal structure and band gap engineering in polyoxometalate-based inorganic-organic hybrids. *Inorg. Chem.* **2016**, *55*, 3364-3377. doi: 10.1021/acs.inorgchem.5b02718
- 21 Q. Z. Zhang, C. Z. Lu. Hydrothermal synthesis and structures of two new molybdenum phosphate compounds based on Keggin cluster units. *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.* **2006**, *632*, 330-334. doi: 10.1002/zaac.200500357
- 22 H. J. Lunk, S. Giese, J. Fuchs, R. Stoesser. Stoesser, Das erste KEGGIN-Anion mit tetraedrischer Kupfer(II)-Sauerstoff-Koordination: $[\alpha\text{-Cu}_0.4(\text{H}_2)_{0.6}\text{O}_4\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{6-}$. *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.* **1993**, *619*, 961-968. doi: 10.1002/zaac.19936190526
- 23 M. V. Marinho, D. O. Reis, W. X. C. Oliveira, L. F. Marques, H. O. Stumpf, M. Déniz, J. Pasán, C. Ruiz-Pérez, J. Cano, F. Lloret, M. Julve. Photoluminescent and slow magnetic relaxation studies on lanthanide(III)-2,5-pyrazinedicarboxylate frameworks. *Inorg. Chem.* **2017**, *56*, 2108-2123. doi: 10.1021/acs.inorgchem.6b02774
- 24 M. Maeda, S. Hino, K. Yamashita, Y. Kataoka, M. Nakano, T. Yamamura, T. Kajiwarra. Correlation between slow magnetic relaxation and the coordination structures of a family of linear trinuclear Zn(II)-Ln(III)-Zn(II) complexes (Ln = Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm and Yb). *Dalton Trans.* **2012**, *41*, 13640-13648. doi: 10.1039/C2DT31399E
- 25 R. Boča, C. Rajnák, J. Titiš, D. Valigura. Field supported slow magnetic relaxation in a mononuclear Cu(II) complex. *Inorg. Chem.* **2017**, *56*, 1478-1482. doi: 10.1021/acs.inorgchem.6b02535
- 26 S. E. Stavretis, M. Atanasov, A. A. Podlesnyak, S. C. Hunter, F. Neese, Z. L. Xue. Magnetic transitions in iron porphyrin halides by inelastic neutron scattering and *Ab Initio* Studies of zero-field splittings. *Inorg. Chem.* **2015**, *54*, 9790-9801.
- 27 M. S. Fataftah, J. M. Zadrozny, S. C. Coste, M. J. Graham, D. M. Rogers, D. E. Freedman. Employing forbidden transitions as qubits in a nuclear spin-free chromium complex. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 1344-1348. doi: 10.1021/jacs.5b11802

Supporting Information for

Incorporation of Cr^{III} into a Keggin polyoxometalate as a chemical strategy to stabilize a labile {Cr^{III}O₄} tetrahedral conformation and promote unattended single-ion magnet properties

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Materials and Methods

The chemicals were reagent grade and used as purchased without further purification. Ammonium metatungstate $(\text{NH}_4)_6[\text{H}_2\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (WO_3 content found (calculated): 92.5 % (92.4 %)) was provided by Global Tungsten & Powders Corp.

Physical methods

Infrared spectrum (4000–400 cm^{-1}) of the sample was recorded on a Bruker Vertex 70 IR Spectrometer equipped with a single-reflection diamond-ATR unit. *Elemental analyses* were performed in aqueous solutions containing 2% HNO_3 using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (PerkinElmer Elan 6000 ICP MS) for Cr and W, and atomic absorption spectroscopy (PerkinElmer 1100 Flame AAS) for Na. Standards were prepared from single-element standard solutions of concentration 1000 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{l}^{-1}$ (Merck, Ultra Scientific and Analytika Prague). Water content was determined by *thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA)* with a Mettler SDTA851e Thermogravimetric Analyzer under air flow with a heating rate of 5 $\text{K} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ in the region 298–1023 K. *Mass spectrometry* was performed with an ESI-Qq-oaRTOF supplied by Bruker Daltonics Ltd. Bruker Daltonics Data Analysis software was used to analyze the results. The measurement was carried out in a 1:1 mixture of $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{MeOH}$, collected in negative ion mode and with the spectrometer calibrated with the standard tune-mix to give an accuracy of ca. 5 ppm in the region of m/z 300–3000. *Cyclic voltammetry* measurements were carried out using a HEKA PG 390 potentiostat at room temperature. A conventional three electrode glass cell of 3 ml capacity was used. A 2 mm diameter glassy carbon disk electrode was used as working electrode (GCE). A platinum wire served as the counter electrode and a normal hydrogen electrode (NHE) as the reference electrode. All solutions were deoxygenated using argon gas for 10–15 min prior to electrochemical experiments. *X-ray powder diffraction* was performed on a Bruker D8 advance diffractometer, Cu $K\alpha$ radiation, $\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$, Lynxeye silicon strip detector and SolX energy dispersive detector, variable slit aperture with 12 mm, $8^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 50$. The *diffuse reflectance spectrum* of a powder sample of CrW_{12} was recorded in the range from 190 to 2550 nm and a step of 1 nm using a double-beam V-670 UV-Visible/NIR spectrophotometer equipped with a unique single monochromator, a horizontal sampling integrating sphere PIN-757 and PMT and a Peltier-cooled PbS detectors for the UV to visible and the NIR regions, respectively.

Synthesis of $\text{Na}_{2.4}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{12}\text{N})_3[\text{CrW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]_{0.6}[\text{H}_2\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]_{0.4} \cdot 37\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (CrW_{12}).

A sample of $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.33 g, 1 mmol) was dissolved in water (50 mL) and HCl [1.0 M] (1.2 mL) was added. $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.0417 g, 0.1 mmol) was dissolved in water (2 mL) and added dropwise to the acidified solution of Na_2WO_4 . The reaction mixture was heated to reflux followed by addition of *tris*(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (0.1 g, 0.8 mmol). The final ratio of reagents was 1 Cr : 10 W : 12 H^+ : 5 Tris- NH_2 . The excess of chromium salt was used to increase the occupancy of Cr^{III} in the Keggin anion. The final pH was 7.5. After refluxing for 24 hours, TMA-Cl was added (0.55 g, 5 mmol) and the solution was cooled to room temperature. The formation of double salt could be connected to the too high solubility of pure TMA- CrW_{12} salt and necessity of several Na^+ ions for crystallization. Yellow crystals were isolated after 2 weeks. Yield: 83 mg (31 % based on W). Elemental analysis found (calculated) for $\text{Na}_{2.4}\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{110.8}\text{N}_3\text{Cr}_{0.6}\text{O}_{77}\text{W}_{12}$: Na 1.37 (1.43), Cr 1.17 (0.82), W 56.2 (57.7). Elements ratio found (calculated): Na : Cr : W = 2.34 (2.4) : 0.88 (0.6) : 12 (12). IR: 3365 (b), 3024 (m), 1645 (m), 1488 (s), 1419 (m), 1342 (m), 1056 (m), 948 (s), 877 (m), 794 (m), 715 (m), 646 (s), 528 (s), 455 (s) cm^{-1} . *Please note:* The Cr^{III} content might slightly vary in different preparations. Four crystals from different batches were measured and X-ray structure analysis revealed no higher Cr occupancy than 60 % and the same disorder of the central ion. The comparison of theoretical and experiential χ_{MT} values points also to partial (36 %) occupancy of the Cr^{III} sites. The possible reaction routes in the $\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}\text{-WO}_4^{2-}$ system between pH 7.5 and 8 applying different Cr and W molar ratios are shown in Scheme S1. The use of NaOH or phosphate buffer to

reach pH 7.5 in the system with the ratio 1.2 Cr : 12 W does not lead to any product isolation and CrW_{12} could crystallize only from the Tris buffered solution. From the system with the ratio 1 Cr: 6 W (pH = 7.7), the tris-functionalized Anderson-type POT was isolated under hydrothermal conditions.¹ At pH 8 crystallization of the unfunctionalized Anderson-type anion is formed.¹ Scheme S1 highlights the complex nature of processes in the Cr-W system and the important influence of pH and Cr to W ratio for end product formation.

Scheme S1. Possible synthetic routes for Cr^{III} and WO_4^{2-} between pH 7.5 and 8 applying two different molar ratios (1:6 and 1.2:12) in the presence and absence of buffering power. The scheme is based on results obtained in this paper and in [1]. Color code: $\{\text{WO}_6\}$, blue or pink; Cr, green; O, red.

Computational Details

DFT calculations were carried out through the Gaussian 09 package in order to estimate the relative stability of TD and SQ molecular geometries of the Cr^{III} ion in CrW_{12} .² These calculations were performed with the PBE pure functional,³ the quadratic convergence approach, a guess function generated with the fragment tool of the same program, and a stability test of the wavefunction. Triple- ζ (TZV) and double- ζ (SV) all-electron basis set proposed by Ahlrichs et al. were used for chromium and oxygen atoms, respectively.⁴ LanL2DZ pseudopotentials were considered to describe the tungsten atoms.⁵ A polarizable continuum model (PCM) was introduced in the calculations with the parameters corresponding to the acetonitrile.⁶

In order to estimate the parameters that determine the axial (D) and rhombic (E) zfs , calculations in an unusual tetrahedral d^3 complex based on complete active space (CASSCF or CAS) methods were performed on CrW_{12} molecule with tetrahedral Cr^{III} ion (occup. 1). Yet this mononuclear species conserves the experimental angular dispositions of the ligands around the metal, and the bond lengths were optimized to correctly calibrate the ligand-field strength of the chloride anions. The optimization geometry was carried out with the Gaussian package using the PBE pure functional and the TZV basis set for all atoms.^{3,4} The CASSCF calculations were carried out with the version 4.0 of the ORCA programme⁷ using the TZVP basis set proposed by Ahlrichs³ and the auxiliary TZV/C Coulomb fitting basis sets.⁸ The contributions to zfs from 10 quartet and 20 doublet excited states generated from an active space with seven electrons in five d orbitals were included using an effective Hamiltonian. The g -tensors were calculated for the ground Kramers pair using Multireference Configuration Interaction (MRCI) wavefunctions with a first-order perturbation theory on the SOC matrix.⁹ RIJCOSX method was used combining resolution of the identity (RI) and "chain of spheres" COSX approximations for the Coulomb and exchange terms, respectively.^{10,11}

Magnetic Measurements

Static direct current (dc) and *ac* measurements were carried out on **CrW₁₂** by powdering and restraining the samples to prevent any displacement due to the magnetic anisotropy. Variable-temperature (2.0–300 K) dc magnetic susceptibility under an applied field of 0.25 (T < 20 K) and 5.0 kG (T ≥ 20 K), and variable-field (0–5.0 T) magnetization in the temperature range from 2 to 10 K were recorded with a Quantum Design SQUID magnetometer. Variable-temperature (2.0–10 K) alternating current (ac) magnetic susceptibility measurements under ±5.0 G oscillating field at frequencies in the range of 0.1–10 kHz were carried out on crystalline samples under different applied static dc fields in the range 0.0–2.5 kG with a Quantum Design Physical Property Measurement System (PPMS). The magnetic susceptibility data were corrected for the diamagnetism of the constituent atoms and the sample holder. HFEPR experiments on powdered samples of **CrW₁₂** were performed using the previously described spectrometer,¹² which was modified with a Virginia Diodes (Charlottesville, VA) source operating at 15.5 ± 3 GHz and generating higher frequencies by a cascade of multipliers. X- and Q-band EPR spectra were recorded in the temperature range 4.0–15 K on a Bruker ER 200 spectrometer equipped with a helium cryostat.

X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) experimental setup and X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) analysis

XAS experiments were performed at beamline B18 at Diamond Light Source, UK. The ring energy was 3.0 GeV and the ring current 300 mA. The beamline was equipped with a Si(111) monochromator in continuous scan acquisition mode. Higher-energy harmonics were rejected using two Pt-coated Si mirrors at 9 mrad incident angle. The absolute energy calibration was performed using chromium foil. The edge position was determined over the first maximum in the first derivative and used for the energy calibration. A Canberra 36-elements monolithic germanium detector and Xspress2 readout electronics was used for the measurements in fluorescence mode. Spectra were collected from 5800 to 6800 eV in continuous scan mode with a step size of 0.2 eV. The spectra of the compounds are the average of 20 scans.

Initially careful radiation damage studies were performed by studying spectra collected at different time intervals. The pre-edge background was removed by a linear approximation in the range of –30 eV to –150 eV before the Cr K-edge. Spectra were normalized by fitting a linear spline function to the post-edge region in ATHENA. The edge position was determined as the maximum in the first derivative of the spectrum (inflection point of the steeply rising edge).

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

The X-ray photoelectron spectra including a survey scan (0–1350 eV) and high-resolution spectra of Cr2p binding energies were recorded on a Thermo Fisher Scientific K-Alpha spectrophotometer (University of Valencia). The spectra were calibrated with the line C1s corresponding to a single C–C bond at 284.84 eV. The analysis of the spectrum (Fig. S13) was achieved by a deconvolution using a mixture of Gaussian and Lorentzian curves in the ratio 0.7:0.3.

X-ray Diffraction on Single Crystals

The X-ray data were measured on a Bruker D8 Venture equipped with a multilayer monochromator, MoK α INCOATEC micro focus sealed tube and Kryoflex cooling device. The structure was solved by direct methods and refined by full-matrix least-squares. Non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters. All calculations were performed by the Bruker SHELXTL (v. 5.1) package and in OLEX2.

Crystal structure description

The main bond lengths and angles in **CrW₁₂** are consistent with those reported for other [XW₁₂O₄₀]ⁿ⁻ anions. The W–O_{terminal}, W–O and W–O_{tet} (O_{tet} – atoms belonging to CrO₈) bond

lengths are in the range of 1.672(11)–1.740(20), 1.837(16)–1.941(16) and 2.283(16)–2.416(18) Å, respectively. The Cr–O_{tet} bond lengths are 1.58(2), 1.62(2) and 1.711(17) Å.

Table S1. Details of data collection and refinement.

	Na_{2.4}(TMA)₃[CrW₁₂O₄₀]_{0.6}[H₂W₁₂O₄₀]_{0.4}·37H₂O
Empirical formula	Cr _{0.60} O ₄₀ W ₁₂ [+ solvent]
CCDC-number	1913668
M _r	2877.40
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	<i>C</i> 2/ <i>m</i>
T, K	100
<i>a</i> , <i>b</i> , <i>c</i> (Å)	15.0892(6)
	21.1101(6)
	13.0805(4)
β (°)	98.788(2)°
V (Å ³)	4117.7(2)
Z	2
D _{calc} , g/cm ³	2.321
μ, mm ⁻¹	31.112
Abs. correction type	multiscan
Abs. correction Tmin	0.055
Abs. correction Tmax	0.424
F(000)	2445.0
Crystal size, mm	0.20 × 0.09 × 0.05
Theta range for data collection	3.19° – 32.54
Index ranges	–17 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 17
	–24 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 24
	–15 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 15
Reflections collected	29032
Independent reflections	3148
R _{int}	0.0365
Data / restraints / parameters	3593/18/141
Goodness-of-fit	1.086
Final <i>R</i> indices	<i>R</i> _F = 0.0724, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.1857 (all data)
	<i>R</i> _F = 0.0666, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.18022 (<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>))
Largest diff. peak and hole, e. Å ⁻³	2.11/-2.94

IR spectrum

The IR spectrum of CrW₁₂ shows all bands expected for a classical Keggin structure (Fig. S1): the terminal W=O stretching vibration appears as a strong band at 948 cm⁻¹, the bands associated with asymmetric W–O–W vibrations within the {W₃O₁₃} triplets at 794 cm⁻¹, and those from W–O–W vibrations involving oxygen bridges between adjacent {W₃O₁₃} triplets at 877 cm⁻¹. The deformation vibrations of W–O–Cr bridging fragments are observed at 455 cm⁻¹, and its stretching vibrations are covered by much stronger W–O–W bands.

Fig. S1. IR spectrum of CrW_{12} .

Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry

The ESI-MS spectrum of CrW_{12} in negative ion mode in mixed $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{MeOH}$ solution reveals, besides small decomposition species, only the doubly- and triply-charged monolacunary Keggin fragments $\text{H}_{7-x-y}\text{Na}_x\text{TMA}_y[\text{CrW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{2-}$ ($x = 1, 2$; $y = 1$) and triple-charged $\text{H}_{6-x-y}\text{Na}_x\text{TMA}_y[\text{CrW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{3-}$ ($x = 1$; $y = 1-4$, see Fig. S2, Table S2).

Fig. S2. Negative ion-mode ESI-MS spectrum of CrW_{12} in $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{MeOH}$ mixture. ESI-MS peak envelopes of $\text{H}_{6-x-y}\text{Na}_x\text{TMA}_y[\text{CrW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{3-}$ (TMA – tetramethylammonium, $x = 1, 2$; $y = 1$ experimental pattern, black; simulated pattern, blue). See Table S2 for the peaks assignment.

Table S2. Species assigned to the peaks in the ESI-MS spectrum of CrW_{12} (see Fig. S2).

	m/z	m/z (calc.)	peak assignment
1	239.9	239.9	$[\text{W}_2\text{O}_7]^{2-}$
2	248.9	248.9	$\text{H}[\text{WO}_4]^-$
3	355.8	355.8	$[\text{W}_3\text{O}_{10}]^{2-}$
4	480.9	480.9	$\text{H}[\text{W}_2\text{O}_7]^-$
5	553.9	553.9	$\text{TMA}[\text{W}_2\text{O}_7]^-$
6	908.8	908.8	$\text{H}_5\text{Na}[\text{CrW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{3-}$
	916.1	916.1	$\text{H}_4\text{Na}_2[\text{CrW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{3-}$
	932.7	932.7	$\text{H}_4\text{Na}(\text{TMA})[\text{CrW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{3-}$
7	1400.7	1400.7	$\text{H}_6\text{Na}(\text{TMA})[\text{CrW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{2-}$
	1437.2	1437.3	$\text{H}_5\text{Na}(\text{TMA})_2[\text{CrW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{2-}$
	1462.9	1462.9	$\text{H}_4(\text{TMA})_3[\text{CrW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{2-}$
	1473.7	1473.3	$\text{H}_3\text{Na}(\text{TMA})_3[\text{CrW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{2-}$
	1499.3	1498.9	$\text{H}_3(\text{TMA})_4[\text{CrW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{2-}$

Electrochemistry

The electrochemical behavior of CrW_{12} and ammonium metatungstate $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{H}_2\text{W}_{12}$ at pH = 7.5 (1 M Na_2SO_4) is shown in Figure S3. The reversible reduction processes observed for both compounds are attributed to the reduction of W^{VI} to W^{V} . The cyclic voltammogram of CrW_{12} exhibits three successive quasi-reversible reduction waves with the half redox potential values $E_{1/2}$ of -0.213, -0.364 and -0.647 V, where $E_{1/2} = (E_{\text{pa}} + E_{\text{pc}})/2$ (E_{pa} and E_{pc} being the anodic and the cathodic peak potentials, respectively). In the cyclic voltammogram of H_2W_{12} two reversible waves are present with $E_{1/2} = -0.006$ V and -0.206 V. The obtained electrochemical data confirmed a known postulate that an increase in the negative charge of the heteropolyanions leads to an increase of the first reduction potential.¹³ Thus, more negative potentials for CrW_{12} (-0.213 V) compared to H_2W_{12} (-0.006 V) indicates predominance of Cr-centered anions with charge 5- over (H_2)-centered anion with charge 6- in CrW_{12} .

Fig. S3. Cyclic voltammograms of CrW_{12} (red line) and $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{H}_2\text{W}_{12}$ (blue line) in 1 M Na_2SO_4 at pH 7.5. Working electrode, glassy carbon (d = 3 mm); reference electrode, normal hydrogen electrode (NHE); scan rate, 50 mV s^{-1} ; concentration of CrW_{12} and H_2W_{12} , 2 mM. The scanning is done in the direction of negative potentials.

Thermogravimetric analysis

Fig. S4. Thermogravimetric curve of CrW₁₂ in the temperature region 25 – 610 °C with a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹.

Powder X-ray diffraction

Fig. S5. Experimental (blue) and simulated (black) X-ray diffraction patterns of CrW₁₂.

Theoretical studies

Based on the density functional theory (DFT), calculations were performed on the possible arrangements of Cr^{III} in CrW₁₂. The calculations revealed that the tetrahedral coordination is more stable by 138.6 kcal/mol than the square-planar.

Usually, complete active space (CAS) calculations allow for estimation of the axial (*D*) and rhombic (*E/D*) components of the *zfs* tensor, as well as the contributions of each excited state to these parameters. Besides the problems in the convergence inherent to this methodology, the study

of a large system with a non-evident electronic structure as in CrW_{12} complicates the choice of the adequate and size-limited active space to build the ground and excited states. Despite the inherent difficulties that go with the *ab initio* methods based on CAS approach (the choice of the adequate active space, the limited size of the active space and the slow or deficient convergence), our calculations on CrW_{12} with tetrahedral Cr^{III} ion (chemical occupancy 1) worked out reliably. The values found for D ($+1.90 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and E/D ratio (0.180) agreed with the experimental estimations. In a similar way as in tetrahedral d^7 complexes, for an ideal tetrahedral d^3 complexes, with ${}^4\text{T}_1$ ground term, a counterbalance of contributions from a 2^{nd} order spin-orbit coupling leads to a null D value. However, distortions should change this situation. In CrW_{12} , the slight loss of symmetry in the $[\text{CrO}_4]^{5-}$ unit causes the weak splitting of this term in three quartet states, with one of them being the ground state. Hence, two low-lying excited quartet states interacting significantly with the ground state do not completely cancel their contributions to the *zfs* tensor. On the other hand, a d^3 configuration in a T_d symmetry should display two excited largely stabilized doublet states, that is the energy gap between them and the ground state should be small or moderate at most. However, this is not the case for CrW_{12} . A partial charge transfer from the oxo groups to the Cr^{III} ion defines the ground state. This fact is not surprising because two groups largely different in the electronic nature, one with a significant electron excess (oxo ligands) and another one with only partially filled orbitals, particularly in an unstable tetrahedral geometry (metal cation), are connected. This large splitting of the ${}^4\text{T}_1$ ground term weakens the individual contributions to D , being the no cancellation of contributions less perceptible (see Table S4). The good agreement of sign and magnitude of D and E/D ratio with the experimental results is also supported by the values of the components of the g tensor for the $M_S = \pm 1/2$ ground Kramers doublet close to those found by EPR, confirming the positive sign of D ($g_1 = 1.80$, $g_2 = 2.83$ and $g_3 = 4.86$).

ACs measurements

The Cole-Cole plots for CrW_{12} in the temperature range 2.0-3.0 K and under applied dc fields of 1000 (Fig. S9a) and 2500 G (Fig. S10b) exhibit semicircle shapes that can be fitted by using the generalized Debye model. In this model, the α parameter is related to the width of the distribution of the relaxation times and takes values between 1 (denoting an infinitely wide distribution of relaxation times) and 0 (describing a single relaxation process). The resulting values for α cover the ranges 0.092-0.128 for the explored temperatures (Table S3). These values are compatible with relaxation processes with well-defined energy barriers.

EPR measurements

Figure S6 shows a typical X-band spectrum and its simulation. The simulation allowed us to disentangle the D and E *zfs* parameters, which is seldom possible through magnetometry, and was not possible from HFEPR in our case.

Figure S7 shows a combined set of conventional (X- and Q-band) EPR and HFEPR data points as a 2-dimensional field vs. frequency (or energy) map. This map is simulated using the spin Hamiltonian parameters given in the main text. Only a few turning points were identifiable in HFEPR spectra but those were attributed with confidence to one of the (nominally) forbidden transition in the $S = 3/2$ spin manifold.

Fig S6. An X-band EPR spectrum of CrW_{12} at 9.4 GHz and 10 K (black trace) accompanied by a simulation (red trace) using zfs parameters as in the main text, and $g = [2.12, 2.12, 1.97]$. Certain features, notably the edge at ca. 118 mT and the line near 200 mT, are not represented in the simulation, which points at a presence of additional spin species, also observed by HFEPR (Figure 3 in the main text). The sharp resonances near $g \sim 2.0$ are radicals and/or defects that are of no concern.

Fig. S7. A field vs. frequency (or energy) dependence of the turning points in the powder spectra of CrW_{12} at low temperatures (4.5 – 10 K). The squares are experimental points; the curves are simulations of all possible turning points that can occur in an $S = 3/2$ spin system using spin Hamiltonian parameters as in the main text. Only the low-field edge of absorption was observable in HFEPR due to poor S/N ratio; however, the simulations confirm the accuracy of the parameters and show that the resonances observed above the zero-field point (65 GHz) are the parallel ($B_0 \parallel z$ -axis of the zfs tensor) turning points of the nominally forbidden $\Delta = \pm 2$ transition such as $| -1/2 \rangle \rightarrow | +3/2 \rangle$ or $| +1/2 \rangle \rightarrow | -3/2 \rangle$.

Fig. S8. Temperature dependence of χ'_M (left) and χ''_M (right) of CrW_{12} in dc applied field of (A) 1.0 and (B) 2.5 kG and under ± 5.0 G oscillating field at frequencies in the range of 0.6 (black line) to 10.0 (green line) kHz.

Fig. S9. Dependence of χ''_{M} of CrW_{12} on the frequency (0.3-10.0 kHz) of the oscillating (± 5.0 G) dc applied field of (A) 1.0 and (B) 2.5 kG.

Fig. S10. Arrhenius plots for CrW_{12} under an applied static field $H_{dc} = 1000 \text{ G}$ (A), $H_{dc} = 2500 \text{ G}$ (B) and with a $\pm 5.0 \text{ G}$ oscillating field at frequencies in the range 1.0-10 KHz and the best fit (black line) to a relaxation process governed by an Orbach mechanism (see text).

Fig. S11. Cole-Cole plots for CrW_{12} in the range from 2.0 to 3.0 K under an applied static field $H_{\text{dc}} = 1000$ G (A) and $H_{\text{dc}} = 2500$ G (B). The solid lines correspond to the best fit according to the Debye model (see Table S3).

XANES measurements

The XANES region at the Cr K-edge, was investigated for CrW_{12} and the Anderson type $\text{Na}_6[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}(\text{OH})_3\text{W}_6\text{O}_{21}]$ as an example of a POT with Cr^{III} in octahedral coordination (Figure S11). The edge shifts for both compounds are calculated at the maximum of the first derivative of the edge and show the same value of 6001 eV in agreement with literature data for Cr^{3+} .¹⁴ The pre-edge peak for 3d-metals, which occurs due to the 1s transition to the p component in d-p hybridized orbital in T_d symmetry or 1s–3d electric quadrupole transition in O_h symmetry, is usually more intense for tetrahedral species than those for octahedral.¹⁵ However, the pre-edge peak intensity for a compound with a tetrahedral center changes as a function of the number of 3d electrons, it is maximized at d^0 and gradually decreases to zero at d^{10} . A simple comparison of the pre-edge peak intensities is not an adequate to evaluate the coordination number of Cr^{III} in this case. The distortion of symmetry from O_h in $\text{Na}_6[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}(\text{OH})_3\text{W}_6\text{O}_{21}]$ can dramatically enhance the pre-edge peak intensity,¹⁵ and the state of $3d^3$ for Cr^{III} weakens the pre-edge peak intensity compared to T_d symmetry for Cr^{VI} .

Fig. S12. Normalized XANES spectra taken at the Cr K-edge of $\text{Na}_6[\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3\text{W}_6\text{O}_{21}]$ and CrW_{12} .

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

To establish the oxidation state of the chromium ion in CrW_{12} , XPS spectra were recorded and analyzed. The Cr2p XPS spectrum displays the characteristic peaks Cr2p_{3/2} and Cr2p_{1/2} at 577.3 and 586.9 eV, respectively (Fig. S13) According to a preliminary XPS study on a surface of chromium oxides Cr₂O₃, which evolves during several chemical processes, the binding energy corresponding to the Cr2p_{3/2} line for different oxidation states for chromium sites should be in the ranges 580.7-581.9 (Cr^{VI}), 577.0-577.6 (Cr^{III}), 576.0-576.7 and 574.3 eV (Cr⁰).¹⁶ Therefore, it is possible to conclude that the chromium ions in CrW_{12} are in plus 3 state.

Fig. S13. XPS spectrum of the CrW_{12} in the binding energies range (569-593 eV) corresponding to the Cr2p lines.

UV-Vis-NIR electronic spectroscopy

The level diagram for the electronic terms for d^3 or d^7 ions show 4F and 4P terms as ground and first excited states. The electronic effect of an electric field induced by ligands coordinated to the metal ion produces a splitting of each of these terms. The resulting Tanabe-Sugano diagrams for d^3 and d^7 ions in tetrahedral and octahedral ligand fields, respectively, are equivalent, being the latter, observed in high-spin cobalt(II) complexes, the most common case in coordination chemistry. The main difference between both cases is the weaker splitting of the d orbitals into e_g and t_{2g} orbitals, provided by the parameter $10Dq$, in the former case, about 4/9 of the last case. In such ones, the splitting of the 4F and 4P terms leads to $^4T_1(F)$, $^4T_2(F)$, $^4A_2(F)$, and $^4T_1(P)$ lower states, which are the ground states for weak or moderate ligand field. The spin-allowed electronic transitions between these states could provide information about the magnitude of the crystal field splitting ($10Dq$) and inter-electronic repulsion parameter (B) defined by the crystal field theory. The UV-Vis-NIR solid reflectance spectrum of CrW_{12} in the range from 350 to 1250 nm (Fig. S14) shows three electronic transitions that were assigned as follows: $^4T_1(F) \rightarrow ^4T_2(F)$ at 8591 cm^{-1} (ν_1 , 1164 nm), $^4T_1(F) \rightarrow ^4A_2(F)$ at 15528 cm^{-1} (ν_2 , 644 nm), and $^4T_1(F) \rightarrow ^4T_1(P)$ at 23095 cm^{-1} (ν_3 , 433 nm). The values of Dq and B obtained for CrW_{12} from the equations $Dq = (\nu_2 - \nu_1)/10$ and $B = (\nu_3 + \nu_2 - 3\nu_1)/15$ are $Dq = 693.7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $B = 856.6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.¹⁷ The low value of Dq , about half of those found in high-spin octahedral d^7 complexes, agrees with a tetrahedral ligand field.¹⁸⁻²² Moreover, the B value lower than that expected for Cr^{III} ion ($B_0 = 1030 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) denotes a significant covalence. This conclusion together with the higher B value than the one proposed for a free Cr^{II} ion

(830 cm^{-1}) supports a moderate charge-transfer from the oxo groups to the Cr^{III} ion. The good agreement of these results with the crystal field theory allows us to establish once again the presence of a high-spin d^3 Cr^{III} ion in a tetrahedral coordination environment.

Fig. S14. UV-Vis-NIR solid reflectance spectrum of CrW_{12} . Thick and thin lines correspond to the experimental and the deconvoluted curves, respectively.

Given that, in an ideal tetrahedral geometry 4T_1 is the ground state, the magnetic behavior of CrW_{12} could be usually induced by a first order spin-orbit coupling (SOC) by coupling between the orbit ($L = 1$) and spin ($S = 3/2$) momenta leading to a splitting into six Kramers doublets in a distorted geometry. The rho parameter is 0.362. In such a case, an approach based on the T-P isomorphism allows to analyze their magnetic properties through the Hamiltonian

$$H = -\alpha\lambda L_{Co}S_{Co} + \Delta \left[L_{z,Co}^2 - \frac{1}{3}L(L+1) \right] + \beta H(-\alpha L_{Co} + g_e S_{Co}) \quad (1),^{23}$$

where λ and α are the spin-orbit coupling constant and the orbital reduction factor defined as $\alpha = A\kappa$. Parameters κ and A account for the reduction of the orbital momentum caused by the delocalization of the unpaired electrons, and the admixture between the ${}^4T_1(P)$ excited and ${}^4T_1(F)$ ground states (A takes values of 1.5 and 1 in the weak and strong crystal-field limits, respectively). Finally, distortion in the tetrahedral coordination sphere leads to a splitting of the ${}^4T_1(F)$ ground state into orbital singlet (4A_2) and doublet (4E) levels, being quantified by the Δ parameter. Best-fit parameters of the thermal dependence on $\chi_M T$ of CrW_{12} below 30 K are: $\alpha = 1.09$, $\lambda = +66.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Delta = +3175 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\text{TIP} = -2326 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ with $F = 5.4 \times 10^{-5}$ (TIP is the temperature-independent paramagnetism and F is the agreement factor defined as $\sum [P_{\text{exp}} - P_{\text{calcd}}]^2 / \sum [P_{\text{exp}}]^2$ where P is the physical property under study). The low values of λ and α are remarkable, being the former largely lower than the value for the free ion ($\lambda_0 = -91 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). From the values of Dq and B determined for CrW_{12} taken from the analysis of their UV-Vis-NIR spectra (see above), a value of A equal to 1.44 for **1** and **2** can be calculated through equation²³:

$$c = 0.75 + 1.875(B/Dq) - 1.25\sqrt{1 + 1.8(B/Dq) + 2.25(B/Dq)^2}$$

$$A = (1.5 - c^2)/(1 + c^2)$$

From the values of α and A previously obtained, κ is found to be equal to 0.76. The values of κ (0.76) and λ/λ_0 (0.74) and B/B_0 (0.83) ratios agree with the strong covalence previously postulated for CrW_{12} .

Table S5. Selected magnetic characteristics for POM-based and 3d transition metals based SIMs/SMMs.

Compound	SIM, $H = 0$	SIM, $H \neq 0$	U_{eff}/K	τ_0/s	Ref.
$\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}$	No	1000 G	3	5.6×10^{-6}	this work
<i>Cr^{II}-based SIMs</i>					
$[\text{Cr}^{\text{II}}(\text{N}(\text{TMS})_2)_2(\text{py})_2]$	No	1500 G	9	1.4×10^{-5}	24
$[\text{Cr}^{\text{II}}(\text{N}(\text{TMS})_2)_2(\text{THF})_2]$	No	2500 G	11.8	2.7×10^{-6}	24
<i>d-block SIMs based on POMs</i>					
$\text{TBA}_7\text{H}_{10}[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{SiW}_9\text{O}_{34})_2]$	No	1000 G	9.2	3.3×10^{-6}	25
$\text{TBA}_7\text{H}_{11}[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{SiW}_9\text{O}_{34})_2]$	No	1000 G	19.3	8.2×10^{-6}	25
<i>f-block SIMs based on POMs</i>					
$\text{Na}_9[\text{ErW}_{10}\text{O}_{36}]$	No	1000 G	55.2	1.6×10^{-8}	26
$[\text{TBA}]_5[\text{Dy}(\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26})_2]$	No	1000 G	38.5	6.6×10^{-8}	27
$[\text{TBA}]_5[\text{Yb}(\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26})_2]$	No	1000 G	23.3	6.7×10^{-6}	27
<i>SMMs based on POMs</i>					
$\text{Na}_4\text{K}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{NO})_7\{[\text{GeW}_9\text{O}_{34}]_2[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}_4\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}_2\text{O}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\}$	No	1000 G	14.8	3.1×10^{-7}	28
$\text{Na}_6(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{12}\text{N})_4[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}_{14}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_9\text{O}_{34})_2]$	No	1000 G	16.7	2×10^{-6}	29
$\text{Na}_{22}\text{Rb}_6\{[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}_4(\text{OH})_3\text{PO}_4]_4(\text{A}-\alpha\text{-PW}_9\text{O}_{34})_4\}$	No	1000 G	26.1	3.5×10^{-8}	30

*SIM, $H = 0$ – SIM behavior in the absence of a dc field;

SIM, $H \neq 0$ – SIM behavior under an applied dc field;

U_{eff} – effective thermal energy barrier;

τ_0 – pre-exponential factor;

TMS = SiMe_3 , py = pyridine, THF = tetrahydrofuran, TBA = tetrabutylammonium.

References

1. N. I. Gumerova, T. Caldera Fraile, A. Roller, G. Giester, M. Pascual-Borràs, C. A. Ohlin, A. Rompel, Direct single- and double-side triol-functionalization of the mixed type Anderson polyoxotungstate $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3\text{W}_6\text{O}_{21}]^{6-}$. *Inorg. Chem.* **2019**, *58*, 106-113; doi: 10.1021/acs.inorgchem.8b01740
2. M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani, V. Barone, B. Mennucci, G. A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, M. Caricato, X. Li, H. P. Hratchian, A. F. Izmaylov, J. Bloino, G. Zheng, J. L. Sonnenberg, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, T. Vreven, J. A. Montgomery, Jr., J. E. Peralta, F. Ogliaro, M. Bearpark, J. J. Heyd, E. Brothers, K. N. Kudin, V. N. Staroverov, R. Kobayashi, J. Normand, K. Raghavachari, A. Rendell, J. C. Burant, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, M. Cossi, N. Rega, J. M. Millam, M. Klene, J. E. Knox, J. B. Cross, V. Bakken, C. Adamo, J. Jaramillo, R. Gomperts, R. E. Stratmann, O. Yazyev, A. J. Austin, R. Cammi, C. Pomelli, J. W. Ochterski, R. L. Martin, K. Morokuma, V. G. Zakrzewski, G. A. Voth, P. Salvador, J. J. Dannenberg, S. Dapprich, A. D. Daniels, Ö. Farkas, J. B. Foresman, J. V. Ortiz, J. Cioslowski, D. J. Fox, Gaussian-09, Gaussian, Inc., Wallingford CT, (2016).
3. J. P. Perdew, K. Burke, M. Ernzerhof, Generalized gradient approximation made simple. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **1996**, *77*, 3865-3868. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.78.1396
4. A. Schaefer, H. Horn, R. Ahlrichs, Fully optimized contracted Gaussian basis sets for atoms Li to Kr. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1992**, *97*, 2571-2577. doi: 10.1063/1.463096

5. P. J. Hay, W. R. Wadt, *Ab initio* effective core potentials for molecular calculations. Potentials for K to Au including the outermost core orbitals. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1985**, *82*, 299-310. doi: 10.1063/1.448975
6. J. Tomasi, B. Mennucci, E. Cancès, The IEF version of the PCM solvation method: an overview of a new method addressed to study molecular solutes at the QM *ab initio* level. *J. Mol. Struct. Theochem.* **1999**, *464*, 211–226. doi: 10.1016/S0166-1280(98)00553-3
7. F. Neese, The ORCA program system. *WIREs Comput. Mol. Sci.* **2012**, *2*, 73-78. doi: 10.1002/wcms.81
8. K. Eichkorn, O. Treutler, H. Ohm, M. Haser, R. Ahlrichs, Auxiliary basis sets to approximate Coulomb potentials. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **1995**, *240*, 283-290. doi: 10.1016/0009-2614(95)00621-A
9. S. Vancoillie, J. Chalupský, U. Ryde, E. I. Solomon, K. Pierloot, F. Neese, L. Rulišek, Multireference *Ab Initio* calculations of g tensors for trinuclear copper clusters in multicopper oxidases. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2010**, *114*, 7692-7702. doi: 10.1021/jp103098r
10. S. Kossmann, F. Neese, Efficient structure optimization with second-order many-body perturbation theory: The RIJCOSX-MP2 method. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2010**, *6*, 2325-2338. doi: 10.1021/ct100199k
11. S. Kossmann, F. Neese, Comparison of two efficient approximate Hartree–Fock approaches. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2009**, *481*, 240-243. doi: 10.1016/j.cplett.2009.09.073
12. A. K. Hassan, L. A. Pardi, J. Krzystek, A. Sienkiewicz, P. Goy, M. Rohrer, L.-C. Brunel, Ultrawide band multifrequency high-field EMR technique: a methodology for increasing spectroscopic information. *J. Magn. Reson.* **2000**, *142*, 300-312. doi: 10.1006/jmre.1999.1952
13. M. Sadakane, E. Steckhan, Electrochemical properties of polyoxometalates as electrocatalysts. *Chem. Rev.* **1998**, *98*, 219-238. doi: 10.1021/cr960403a
14. M. Tromp, J. Moulin, G. Reid, J. Evans, Cr K-Edge XANES spectroscopy: ligand and oxidation state dependence – what is oxidation state? *AIP Conference Proceedings* **2007**, *882*, 699-702. doi: 10.1063/1.2644637
15. T. Yamamoto. Assignment of pre-edge peaks in K-edge x-ray absorption spectra of 3d transition metal compounds: electric dipole or quadrupole? *X-Ray Spectrom.* **2008**, *37*, 572-584. doi: 10.1002/xrs.1103
16. B. P. Liu, P. Sindelar, Y. W. Fang, K. Hasebe, M. Terano, Correlation of oxidation states of surface chromium species with ethylene polymerization activity for Phillips CrO_x/SiO₂ catalysts modified by Al-alkyl cocatalyst. *J. Mol. Catal. A-Chem.* **2005**, *238*, 142-150. doi:10.1016/j.molcata.2005.05.015
17. A. B. P. Lever, *Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
18. A. A. Razik, A. K. Abdel Hadi, Synthesis and spectral studies of chromium(III), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes with phenylhydrazonoamidoxime *Transition Metal Chem.* **1994**, *19*, 84-86. doi: 10.1007/BF00166275
19. M. A. Maldonado-Rogado, E. Viñuelas-Zahínos, F. Luna-Giles, F.J. Barros-García, Synthesis and structural characterization of cobalt(II) and zinc(II) complexes with 2-(indazol-1-yl)-2-thiazoline (TnInA). X-ray characterization of [CoCl₂(TnInA)₂]·C₂H₆O and [(M)(TnInA)₂(H₂O)₂](NO₃)₂ (M = Co, Zn). *Polyhedron* **2007**, *26*, 5210-5218. doi: 10.1016/j.poly.2007.07.043
20. D. Shukla, L. K. Gupta, S. Chandra, Spectroscopic studies on chromium(III), manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes with hexadentate nitrogen-sulfur donor [N(2)S(4)] macrocyclic ligand. *Spectrochim. Acta A* **2008**, *71*, 746-750. doi: 10.1016/j.saa.2007.12.052

21. E. Soleimani, Synthesis, characterization and anti-microbial activity of a novel macrocyclic ligand derived from the reaction of 2,6-pyridinedicarboxylic acid with homopiperazine and its Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), and Zn(II) complexes. *J. Mol. Struct.* **2011**, *995*, 1-8. doi: 10.1016/j.molstruc.2011.01.002
22. A. Świtlicka, J. Palion-Gazda, B. Machura, J. Cano, F. Lloret, M. Julve. Field-induced slow magnetic relaxation in pseudooctahedral cobalt(ii) complexes with positive axial and large rhombic anisotropy. *Dalton Trans.* **2019**, *48*, 1404-1417. doi: 10.1039/C8DT03965H
23. F. Lloret, M. Julve, J. Cano, E. Pardo, Magnetic properties of six-coordinated high-spin cobalt(II) complexes: Theoretical background and its application. *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2008, **361**, 3432-3445. doi: 10.1016/j.ica.2008.03.114
24. Y.-F. Deng, T. Han, Z. Wang, Z. Ouyang, B. Yin, Z. Zheng, J. Krzystek, Y.-Z. Zheng, Uniaxial magnetic anisotropy of square-planar chromium(II) complexes revealed by magnetic and HF-EPR studies. *Chem. Commun.* **2015**, *51*, 17688-17691. doi: 10.1039/c5cc07025b
25. R. Sato, K. Suzuki, T. Minato, M. Shinoe, K. Yamaguchi, N. Mizuno, Field-induced slow magnetic relaxation of octahedrally coordinated mononuclear Fe(III)-, Co(II)-, and Mn(III)-containing polyoxometalates. *Chem. Commun.* **2015**, *51*, 4081-4084. doi: 10.1039/C4CC09435B
26. M. A. AlDamen, J. M. Clemente-Juan, E. Coronado, C. Martí-Castaldo, A. Gaita-Ariño, Mononuclear lanthanide single-molecule magnets based on polyoxometalates. *Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, *130*, 8874-8875. doi: 10.1021/ja801659m
27. J. J. Baldoví, Y. Duan, C. Bustos, S. Cardona-Serra, P. Gouzerh, R. Villanneau, G. Gontard, J. M. Clemente-Juan, A. Gaita-Ariño, C. Giménez-Saiz, A. Proust, E. Coronado, Single ion magnets based on lanthanoid polyoxomolybdate complexes. *Dalton Trans.* **2016**, *45*, 16653-16660. doi: 10.1039/C6DT02258H
28. C. Ritchie, A. Ferguson, H. Nojiri, H. N. Miras, Y.-F. Song, D.-L. Long, E. Burkholder, M. Murrie, P. Kögerler, E. K. Brechin, L. Cronin, Polyoxometalate-mediated self-assembly of single-molecule magnets: {[XW₉O₃₄]₂[Mn(III)₄Mn(II)₂O₄(H₂O)₄]}¹²⁻. *Angew. Chem.* **2008**, *47*, 5609-5612. doi: 10.1002/anie.200801281
29. J.-D. Compain, P. Mialane, A. Dolbecq, I. M. Mbomekallé, J. Marrot, F. Sécheresse, E. Riviere, G. Rogez, W. Wernsdorfer, Iron polyoxometalate single-molecule magnets. *Angew. Chem.* **2009**, *121*, 3123-3127. doi: 10.1002/ange.200900117
30. M. Ibrahim, Y. Lan, B. S. Bassil, Y. Xiang, A. Suchopar, A. K. Powell, U. Kortz, Hexadecacobalt(II)-containing polyoxometalate-based single-molecule magnet. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2011**, *50*, 4708-4711. doi: 10.1002/anie.201100280